

THE PERCEIVED QUALITY OF SERVICES PROVIDED ON INDUSTRIAL PARK PLATFORMS

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Abstract

Today, which is characterized by economic growth, technological, environmental, and social change, it is hard to focus our business on goods and services that match social needs while being eco-friendly. There is no doubt that the urban environment provides numerous opportunities for relaxation and recreation; however, pollution (atmospheric and noise) in urban agglomerations produces states that are associated with a high mild discomfort. In this context, industrial parks seem to be solid business development alternatives. Thus, we conducted research in which we aimed to study the influence of the communication relationship between the industrial park management team (IP) on the line of perception of service quality. Concurrently, the research investigated the influence of communication with managerial staff at the company where the employee works on the employee's perceptions of quality of services received in the IP.

Keywords: communication, industrial park, perceptions, quality services

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1. Introduction

Service companies need to develop a clear and precise employee training strategy; strategy to achieve the proposed objectives, but also to take into account both the needs of employees and future beneficiaries. Therefore, Lovelock and Wirtz (2011, pp. 294-295) summarized the fact that training staff in the field of services requires an organizational strategy, personal, interpersonal, technical skills and very good knowledge of the product.

In this context, the organizational strategy must be assimilated by the staff employed in order to achieve the objective of promoting the values of the economic entity. This knowledge must include elements of identity and history (company history, culture, philosophy and objectives, mutual respect, team spirit and integrity); all this being reflected, then, in the excellence of the services provided.

On the other hand, personal, interpersonal and technical skills are essential for the provision of quality services. Personal and interpersonal skills (eg: active listening, techniques associated with non-verbal communication, establishing eye contact) have the role of facilitating communication with customers, but also to increase the perception of the quality of service provided. At the same time, the technical skills (eg: thorough knowledge in the field, required and imposed rules and regulations, various procedures, ability to use the equipment and operate the machines required in the production process of the service) have the role of generating a level high level of confidence in terms of professionalism and, implicitly, the quality of the service provided.

Levin and Wright (1997) point out that, despite high acquisition costs, individuals who become owners are reluctant to relocate, even if this involves additional resources. It should also be noted that for a large part of the population the building is the expression of the main form of ownership. Or, from this perspective, at a time when the real estate market is on an upward trend, the perception is changing.

The important role of industrial parks is to support local economic development (LED), as the study by The Urban Institute shows: "Once the need for new investors is recognized, local authorities can start doing so by creating prosperous for business. One of the most important preconditions for a proactive approach in attracting foreign and domestic investors is the creation of an industrial park, by ensuring a fully equipped industrial site" (The Urban Institute, 2008).

The management of industrial parks (public, private or mixed) is carried out by companies. Therefore, the management team (IP) is directly involved in the decision-making process and ensuring their optimal operation. Thus, we appreciate that their views are important in terms of the quality of services in industrial parks.

The establishment of industrial parks aims at stimulating the economic and social development, contributing to the technological transfer, to attracting investments and to capitalize on the human resources of the area. However, their role is to ensure that companies operating within their perimeter have access to the infrastructure and full utilities necessary to carry out economic activities. Industrial parks are usually managed by a company.

2. Methodology

The questionnaire was used to collect data between June and August 2021, and it was used both physically and online, using Google's Forms tool. We note that 125 replies were recorded online, and 225 hard copies were made. As a result, the sample (350 respondents) included 150 employees of companies that operate on the platforms of industrial parks in Bihor, 150 employees of companies that operate on the platforms of industrial parks in Cluj, 25 employees of companies that operate on the platforms of operational industrial parks in Satu Mare, and 25 employees of companies that operate on the platforms of operational industrial parks in Bistrița.

In order to conduct this research, we proposed the following research hypothesis:

H1 The perceived quality of the services received in the industrial parks is directly and positively influenced by the perceived service.

3. Results

We wanted to highlight how employees (who work for firms that are part of the industrial parks platform) feel about the quality of services provided by these parks. Through the perspective of the reception-use-response process, we were able to assess employee perceptions of the quality of services obtained on the industrial park platform.

We note that an important element is the extent to which employees appreciate the content of the services received. Thus, the received answers show that 70.28% of the respondents appreciate this positively, about a third considering it as very good. On the other hand, only 6% consider it negative, and 23.72% are satisfied with the content of the services received. The

usefulness of the services received is rated as good and very good in the proportion of 73.72%, satisfactory (19.43%) and as poor or very poor (6.86%).

Regarding the relevance of the services received, the same trend can be noticed, respectively 69.43% of the respondents have a positive opinion, 22.86% of them are satisfied with the relevance of the services and only 7.72% appreciate these as irrelevant services. Also, almost 66% of those surveyed consider the services received to be up-to-date and only about 12% consider them outdated. We note that the difference up to 100% is represented by the respondents who indicated that they are satisfied with the timeliness of the services received on the platform of the industrial park in which they operate.

The capacity and professionalism of the team leading the industrial park is appreciated as good / very good by over 71% of respondents and weak / very weak by 6.85% of them, and 22% are satisfied with the management team of the industrial park. 73.64% of those surveyed consider that they use the received services very well, while 20.29% consider that they use these services satisfactorily and only 6% consider that they do not use these services well.

The need for these services is perceived positively (71.14%), of which 26% give a very good rating and 45.14% a good rating. The percentage of those who appreciate this negatively is 7.71% (corresponding to the rating of poor), while 21.14% gave the rating of satisfactory. The percentage of respondents who appreciate the services received as important for them is 74.57%, while 16.86% give an average rating in terms of the importance of services and only 8.57% consider them as unimportant. The positive answers regarding the received services total a number of 264 which represents over 75.42% of the total respondents, while 18.57% seem undecided and only 6% gave a negative answer.

Therefore, respondents indicate a positive perception of the services received, how they use them and how they respond to their offer.

The most common value for the answers related to the analyzed variable (Perception of services by workers, considering the process of receiving-using-answering) indicates the good level (code 4) (Table 1).

Table 1: Indicator of the central trend for the perceived influence variable of the service received considering the process of receiving - use - response

N	Valid	350
	Missing	0
Mode		4.00
Minimum		1.00
Maximum		5.00

Source: Data analysis using IBM SPSS

According to the first hypothesis H1 The perceived service directly and positively influences the perceived quality of the services received in the industrial parks, an aggregate indicator of the appreciations of the notions that make up the perceived service regarding the received-use-response process was calculated. This indicator was also calculated for the variable that takes into account the perceived quality of services received in an industrial park. We also calculated the Spearman correlation coefficient, the following result was obtained, the data indicating the existence of a significant positive correlation, and the value of the coefficient $p = 0.01$ shows us that this link has a statistical value. (Table 2)

Table 2: Correlation between perceived service on the receive-use-response process and perceived quality of services in industrial parks

			Q ₁	Q ₉
Spearman`s rho	Q ₁	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.687**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	350	350
	Q ₉	Correlation Coefficient	.687**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	350	350

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Note: Q₁ - the perceived service regarding the receiving-use-response process; Q₉ - perceived quality of services in industrial parks

The statistical significance of the regression was determined using ANOVA analysis which resulted in a statistically significant coefficient of 0.01 (Table 3)

Table 3: ANOVA analysis result

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	151.531	1	151.531	345.322	.000 ^b
	Residual	154.009	348	.413		
	Total	305.540	349			
a. Dependent Variable: Q ₉ perceived quality of services in industrial parks						
b. Independent Variable: (Constant) Q ₁ the perceived service regarding the receiving-use-response process						

Calculating the linear regression on the two variables, the coefficient R² (Table 4), we can say that 49.5% of the variation of assessments regarding the perceived quality of services provided by industrial parks is justified based on the assessment of perceived service that considers the process receive-use-answer.

Table 4 Result obtained by applying the linear regression between the appreciation of the perceived service regarding the receive-use-response process and the perceived quality of the services offered by the industrial parks

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Str. Error of the Estimate
1	.705 ^a	.497	.495	.650
a. Independent: (Constant), Q ₁ the perceived service regarding the receiving-use-response process				

Thus, we can conclude that the hypothesis H1 *The perceived service directly and positively influences the perceived quality of the services received in the industrial parks* **is confirmed.**

4. Conclusions

A significant percentage appreciate as good or even very good the content, usefulness and relevance of the services received, a small percentage (well below 10%) do not appreciate these things. Therefore, we can appreciate the fact that, in the industrial parks in Romania, the beneficiaries have at their disposal a good package of services meant to improve their quality of life. Positive assessments were also registered regarding the professionalism of the industrial park management team. We note that four items related to the

employee's life received lower ratings. Thus, from the point of view of the connection of the perceived service regarding the reception-use-response service and the perceived quality of the services offered by the industrial parks, it outlines the existence of a good intensity correlation. In other words, the services offered by industrial parks could be improved both in terms of content and quality.

5. References

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